

Variety of Languages Private Radio Broadcast in DKI Jakarta

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Abstract:-Radio broadcasters, both government radio broadcasters, in this case Radio Republik Indonesia (RRI) broadcasters and private radio broadcasters have an important role in delivering news or conversations to their listeners. For this reason, broadcasters should be able to apply the use of the Indonesian language properly and correctly both in the context of official and unofficial broadcasts. The purpose of this research is 1) to show language interference on private radio broadcasters in DKI Jakarta, and 2) to describe language interference on private radio broadcasters in DKI Jakarta. This research used descriptive qualitative method that describing the grammatical and lexical interference of private radio broadcasters in DKI Jakarta. This research applied Weinreich's theory (1970), which stated that interference is the use of two languages by someone which can sometimes lead to deviations from the norms of each language. The results show that in broadcasting there are 1) non-Indonesian grammatical interference into Indonesian, 2) non-Indonesian lexical interference into Indonesian.

Keywords:-Bilingualism, grammatical interference, lexical interference.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesian language as a means of communication between members of society includes two varieties of language, namely spoken and written. This statement is in accordance with Sunaryo (2000: 24) that Indonesian as a communication tool includes two things, such as the variety of spoken language and the variety of writing. As an oral variety, it is supported by situations of use. As a spoken variety of Indonesian, for instance, it is used by radio broadcasters, both government and private radio broadcasters.

Radio broadcasters, both government radio broadcasters, in this case Radio Republik Indonesia (RRI) broadcasters and private radio broadcasters, have an important role in conveying or broadcasting news or chats for their listeners. For this reason, broadcasters should be able to apply the use of the Indonesian language properly and correctly both in the context of official and unofficial broadcasts. The broadcaster, considers the interlocutor, in this case the radio broadcast listener. In addition, the broadcaster should be able to choose the right vocabulary, so that it does not make it difficult for listeners to understand and understand the information broadcast by the broadcaster (Akpan et al., 2012).

According to Winarti (1995: 2) radio broadcasters should master the language used or be able to apply the language used in their broadcasts because the use of good language will make radio broadcasts interesting and liked by their audience. Apart from that, the number of languages used by radio broadcasters will affect the community of fans and listeners (Hallett & Hintz, 2010).

Listen to private radio broadcasts, both official and unofficial broadcasts, it perceived the use of language well, it means that several languages are used in broadcasting the news. For example, in broadcasts in Indonesian there are still elements of regional languages, such as it still implied in Javanese, Sundanese including slang or Prokem in broadcasts which should use Indonesian.

The examples of non-Indonesian language used as follows.

The use of nasalized forms of regional languages and dialects.

Bagaimana perasaan kamu kalau ternyata teman yang nyontek abis-abisan ternyata nilainya lebih bagus dari kamu yang belajar mati-matian. (Prambos)

How would you feel if it turned out that your friend who cheated like crazy was getting better grades than you who studied like hell. (Prambos)

Yang Namanya nyontek udah akrab banget deh sama kawula muda. (Prambos)

The name of cheating is very familiar with young people. (Prambos)

Beki pengen ngirim tembang aja deh. (Prambos)

Beki wants to send me a song. (Prambos)

The forms of 'nyontek' and 'ngirim' are not forms of nasalization of the Indonesian language, but forms of nasalization of the Jakarta dialect of Malay. That form in Indonesian starts with meN- and meN-kan so it becomes 'copying' and sending. Thus, the forms of 'cheating' and 'send' in the language of the radio announcer are influenced by the Jakarta dialect of Malay. Thus, the forms of 'cheat' and 'sent' used by radio broadcasters are forms of interference.

The case mentioned above is a case encountered in the use of Indonesian by private radio broadcasters in DKI. Therefore, the researcher conduct this research further about the interference of private radio broadcasters in DKI. The purpose of this research is to describe the language interference of private radio broadcasters in DKI which includes the following. 1. Grammatical interference, namely at the level of morphology, syntax, and lexical interference. 2. The frequency of interference according to the type of level, namely grammatical interference at the level of morphology, syntax, and lexical interference. 3. Factors that cause interference. 4. The correlation between the frequency of interference with the presentation of broadcast monologues and dialogues.

This research is important to know for the public the various languages of radio broadcasters to be understood because it can maintain harmonious relations between speakers. Speech is delivered with the intention of implicitly criticizing or satirizing, it is hoped that there will be no offense and misunderstanding so that the public can communicate properly without any doubts in communicating, so that the information conveyed by the broadcaster can be received easily. This is related to the Indonesian culture which upholds courtesy, including in communication. Therefore, this research is important to help the ongoing good communication.

II. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Based on the previous section, the objective of this study is formulated as follows: 1) Constructing exclusive sum labeling on gear graphs. 2) Obtaining isolated vertex sums for exclusive sum labeling on geargraphs. The data will be categorized in exclusive sum labeling on geargraph by Leonhard Euler. have fulfilled.

A. Diglossia

In sociolinguistics, it is known that there is diglossia. One variety is considered higher than the other, so that in a language society two varieties of language develop, namely high variety and low variety (Moeliono, 1985: 86). In the same regard, Suwito (1993: 44) also stated that diglossia is a condition where two languages are used in the same society, but each language has its own function and role in a social context. On the other hand, as Kridalaksana (1993:44) stated that diglossia is a language situation with existing language divisions and variations. One language variation is given a "high" status used for official use, while the other language variations have a "lower" status which is used for informal communication and its structure is adapted to the flow of communication (Schiffman, 2017).

In connection with the views of the experts above, it is necessary to explain diglossia in this research because the data used by researchers is a developing language or the language used in the audience or the wider community. Based on some of the explanation above, it is agreed that there are two varieties of Indonesian that are developing in the Indonesian language user community, especially the Indonesian language community in DKI Jakarta, namely the high variety and the low variety.

B. Bilingualism

According to Kridalaksana (1993: 31) bilingualism is the use of two or more languages by a person or society. Bilingualism can be divided into three, namely coordinate bilingualism, multiple bilingualism, and subordinate bilingualism (García et al., 2014; Zakaria et al., 2021). Coordinate bilingualism is bilingualism with separate language systems or more (a person who is coordinate bilingualism when using one language does not reveal elements of another language and when switching to another language there is no system mixing) (Mabule, 2015; Hamuddin et al., 2020). Multiple bilingualism is bilingualism with two or more integrated language systems (someone who is multiple bilingual often confuses the elements of the two languages or the languages they master) (Wei, 2020). Subordinate bilingualism is bilingualism with two separate language systems, but there is still a compounding process (a person who is bilingual subordinate usually/tends to mix the concepts of his first language into his second language) (Antoniou, 2019; Rahman et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, Nababan (1993:27-29) stated that bilingualism is the habit of using two languages in integrating with other people. In other words, bilingualism is not only used by individuals, but also for society. The rapid progress in the field of information in the field of electronics on means (Grosjean, 2013; Andini et al., 2022).

Language contact that continuously produces people who can master more than one language (Rahman, 2018; Sukmawaty et al., 2022). It can pay attention to this or listen to it when a radio announcer is in language contact during the program of the listener's choice, both dialogue and monologue. Such an atmosphere will result in a broadcaster using more than one language. This happened, considering that the target audience is various ethnic groups in this DKI area.

C. Interference

Talking about interference is one of the cases that cannot be avoided because there is mutual disadvantage in the existence of each language. This happens when radio broadcasters are interacting in their programs, they tend to use more than two languages when interacting with their listeners (Van Dyke, 2012). Such cases of language deviation are called interference.

Weinreich (1970: 1) stated that interference is a deviation from the norms of each that occurs in bilingual speech due to the introduction of more than one language.

Fishman et al., (1975: 569) stated that interference is the use of elements belonging to one language when speaking or writing in another language. It is evident that when radio broadcasters speak in their broadcast programs, they consciously or unconsciously use a language other than Indonesian.

In connection with this research, the researcher tends to use Wairaeich's theory, namely deviations from the norms of each language. For this study, the data obtained were analyzed according to Weinreich's view, that are syntactical, morphological and lexical interference. In other words, morphological and syntactic interference is called grammatical interference.

III. METHOD

This research used a descriptive qualitative method that requires categories as units of analysis. Therefore, various categories are made based on theoretical references both form and purpose, as well as inductive categories. Furthermore, the researcher applied an inductive design, Moleong (1990: 6). In accordance with Moleong's view, this research was conducted by describing the grammatical and lexical interference in the language of private radio broadcasters in Jakarta. This research is categorized as qualitative because it will classify the selected data for further analysis. Data source

The source of the data used in this research is the language of radio broadcasters Prambos, SK radio, and TMI radio. The data referred to has been written and recorded previously, namely June-August. The data were taken randomly. The consideration for taking data from the broadcasters was because the radios were well known to the public, with their programs, such as quizzes, or requests for songs from listeners. The data collection techniques are carried out by recording and writing data related to grammatical interference. The data in question is data from radio broadcasters, both male and female broadcasters.

IV. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

This research aims to 1) to show language interference on private radio broadcasters in DKI Jakarta, and 2) to describe language interference on private radio broadcasters in DKI Jakarta.

V. FINDINGS

From the data that has been collected, interference is a language problem in the language of private radio broadcasters in DKI. Thus, this session discussed about interference in the language of private radio broadcasters in DKI.

Discussion of interference in this part will be grouped into two categories, namely grammatical interference and lexical interference. In the following, each section will be discussed. In this sub-chapter, the frequency of language interference of radio broadcasters will be explained, namely broadcast presentation, broadcast topics, and broadcaster gender. The number of sentences from the radio broadcaster language data that the author managed to collect was 989 sentences. Of the 989 data, 303 sentences from the radio announcer's language contained interference. And those that do not contain interference are 584 sentences. In one sentence sometimes more than one word contains interference.

A. Interference Frequency Based on Broadcast Presentation

a) The number of language disturbances based on the presentation of private radio broadcasters is 315 words out of 303 sentences, b) The amount of morphological interference in the language of private broadcasting institutions is based on the presentation of 118 words (37.46%). c) The number of morphological interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on monologue presentations was 77 words (30.79%). d) The number of morphological interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on the presentation of the dialogue is 21 words (6.6%). e) The number of syntactic interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on broadcast presentation is 111 words (35, 24%). f) The total syntactic intensity of the private radio announcer's language based on the presentation of the monologue is 80 words (25.40%). g) The number of interference based on the dialogue is 31 words (9.84%). h) The amount of lexical interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on the presentation of the dialogue is 31 words (9.84%). I) The amount of lexical interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on the

monologue presentation is 71 words (22.54%). j) The amount of lexical interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on the presentation of radio dialogue is 15 words (4.76%). k) The total language interference of private radio broadcasters based on monologue presentation is 248 words (78, 73%). l) The amount of language interference made by private radio broadcasters based on the presentation of the dialogue is 67 words (21.27%).

B. Interference Frequency Based on Broadcast Topic

a) The number of private radio announcer language interference based on the presentation is 315 words of 303 sentences. b) Number of morphological interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on presentation is 118 words (37.46%). c) Number of morphological interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on presentation monologue is 105 words (33, 33 %). d) Number of morphological interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on presentation dialogue is 13 words (4.13%). e) Number of syntactical interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on broadcast presentation is 111 words (35, 24%). f) Number of syntactic inefficiency of language of private radio broadcasters based on presentation monologue is 101 words (32.06 %). g) The amount of interference based on the dialogue is 10 words (3.17%). h) Number of lexical interference Private broadcaster language based on presentation dialogue is 86 words (27.30%). I) The amount of lexical interference in the

language of the broadcaster's language is based on private radio broadcasters monologue presentation is 80 words (25.40%). j) The number of lexical interference in the language of private radio broadcasters based on radio presentation dialogue is 6 words (1.90%). k) The number of private broadcasters' language interference based on monologue presentations is 286 words (90.79%). l) The amount of language interference for private radio broadcasters based on the presentation of the dialogue is 29 words (9, 20 %).

C. Based on the Serving Variable

The presentation variable can be divided into two, namely the presentation of the monologue and the presentation of the dialogue. In the following, both of these will be discussed.

➤ Monologue Presentation

There are three things that will be discussed in the presentation of the monologue, namely the use of nasalized forms, the use of basic forms of Indonesian + local language affixes and dialects + Indonesian affixes.

• The Use of Nasalized Forms

The interference that occurs in the language of private radio broadcasters in DKI seen from the form of nasalization can be grouped into two, namely the use of the nasalized form of the regional language and its dialect and the use of the nasalized form of a foreign language.

The Use of Nasalized Forms of Regional Languages and Dialects	
Nyontek	: Bagaimana perasaan kamu kalau ternyata teman yang nyontek abis-abisan ternyata nilainya lebih bagus dari kamu yang belajar mati-matian. (Prambos) How would you feel if it turned out that a friend who cheated a lot turned out to have better grades than you who studied like hell. (Prambos)
Ngirim	: Beki pingin ngirim tembang aja deh. (Prambos) Beki wants to send me a song. (Prambos)
Ngejawab	: Beki pingin ngirim tembang aja deh. (Prambos) Later, when Beki show the quiz title, be prepared to answer. (Prambos)
Ngasi	: Nah, makanya kalau kamu pingin ngasi support ke mereka, kamu bisa langsung datang aja ke Prambos Cafe. (Prambos) So, if you want to provide support for them, you can just come to Prambos Cafe. (Prambos)

The form of the word above is not a standard Indonesian form. These forms are forms of nasalization originating from the Jakarta dialect of Malay.

The forms of nasalization of the Jakarta dialect of Malay in Indonesian start with meN- and meN-kan derived from the root words of the Jakarta dialect of Malay, kasi, saying, and what are prefixed with ng and ng-in.

• The Use of Forms of Foreign Language Nasalization

The form of ngefen in the sentence above is not a standard Indonesian form. The basic form of nasalization comes from English, namely fens and is given the affix ng which comes from the Jakarta dialect of Malay.

Thus, the use of the ngefens form is an influence from English which is prefixed with the Jakarta dialect of Malay.

The Use of Indonesian Basic Forms + Local Language Affixes and their Dialects

- Marahin : Ada seorang bapak yang akhir-akhir ini marahin anaknya. (SK)
There is a father who has recently been angry with his son. (SK)
- Dengerin : Sekarang kamu dengerin perbincangan saya dengan seorang mistery quest atau bintang tamu yang muncul di acara kuis TMI. (TMI).
Now you listen to my conversation with a mystery quest or guest star who appears on the TMI quiz show. (TMI).
- Bacain : Sekarang kamu dengerin perbincangan saya dengan seorang mistery quest atau bintang tamu yang muncul di acara kuis TMI. (TMI).
This time, we first read some information from news excerpts from the general daily Suara Pembaruan, published today, Tuesday, August 16, 1994. (TMI)

The sentence above is not standard Indonesian. These forms are affixed forms derived from the basic forms of the Indonesian language and are given augmentation derived from the basic forms of the Jakarta dialect of Malay. The forms of

Jakarta dialect Malay in Indonesian are prefixes meN-, meN-i, meN-kan, ber-, per-kan, endings -i, di-i, di-kan, and -kan. In the Jakarta dialect, the suffix-an is used after all consonants except /b/, /d/, /g/ (Muhajir, 1984:57).

2) The Use of Basic Forms of Regional Languages and Dialects + Indonesian Additions

- Dibilang : Seperti udah dibilang berkali-kali kita ngebahas soal di Jakarta dalam rangka hari bumi kemarin ini. (Prambos)
As has been said many times, we discussed matters in Jakarta in the context of Earth Day yesterday. (Prambos)
- Seabrek : Soalnya, bahannya seabrek banget. (Prambos)
The thing is, the material is really thick. (Prambos)
- Kepingin : Kalau kamu kepingin ngasi support ke mereka, kamu bisa langsung aja ke Prambos Cafe. (Prambos)
If you want to give support to them, you can just go to Prambos Cafe. (Prambos)

The forms in the sentence above are not standard Indonesian forms. These forms are forms of affixes whose basic form comes from the Jakarta dialect of Malay and Javanese and the affixes come from Indonesian.

Thus, the use of the forms of the words above in the language of the radio announcer is an influence from the Jakarta dialect of Malay and Javanese. So, the forms of affixes used by radio broadcasters are a form of distortion or interference.

1. Dialogue Presentation

There are three things that will be discussed in the presentation of the dialogue, namely the use of nasalized forms, the use of the basic forms of Indonesian + regional language affixes and their dialects, and the basic forms of regional languages and dialects + Indonesian affixes.

➤ *The Use of Nasalized Forms*

The interference found in the language of private radio broadcasters in DKI seen from the form of nasalization is the use of nasalized forms originating from regional languages and dialects.

- The Use of Forms of Nasalization of Language and Dialects

Ngucapin	:	Sebelumnya dari Terminal Musik Indonesia ngucapin selamat siang terus mohon maaf kalau mengganggu. (TMI). Previously, Terminal Musik Indonesia said good afternoon and apologized for disturbing. (TMI).
Ngelapor	:	nggak usah ngelapor no need to report

The form of the word above is not a standard Indonesian form. These forms are forms of nasalization of the Jakarta dialect of Malay. The forms of nasalization of the Jakarta

dialect of Malay in Indonesian begin with meN- and meN-kan. So, the forms used by radio broadcasters are a form of deviation or interference

- The Use of Indonesian Basic Forms + Local Language Affixes and their Dialects

Ikutan	:	Saya tutup dahulu karena saya mau buka telepon untuk yang ikutan. (TMI) I hang up first because I want to open the phone for those who join. (TMI)
Dihargain	:	Paling kalau lihat yang nyontek dihargain aja usahanya. (Prambos) It's dizzy when you see someone who cheats and their business is appreciated. (Prambors)

The forms of the words above are not standard Indonesian. These forms are affixed forms derived from the basic forms of the Indonesian language and are affixed with the

Jakarta dialect of Malay. The forms of the Jakarta dialect Malay Mahasa in Indonesian are the prefixes ber-, meN-kan, per-kan, di-i –kan

- The Use of the basic forms of regional languages and their dialects + Indonesian affixes

Dikasi	:	Mesti dikasi hadiah special. (Prambos) Must be given a special gift. (Prambors)
Mengasi	:	Silahkan mengasi opini. (Prambos) Please give your opinion. (Prambors)

The forms of dication and mengasi in the sentences above are not standard forms of Indonesian. These forms are forms of affixes whose basic form comes from the Jakarta dialect of Malay and the affixes come from Indonesian. The forms of giving and giving in Indonesian are giving and giving. Thus, the use of the forms of dikasi and mengasi in the language of the radio announcers is influenced by the Jakarta dialect of Malay. So, the forms of cation and mengasi used by radio broadcasters are a form of deviation or interference.

VI. CONCLUSION

The results of the data analysis that has been carried out in the previous chapter, can be drawn the following conclusions. The use of the language of private radio broadcasters in Jakarta is marked by interference from the Jakarta dialect of Malay, Javanese, and Sundanese, or even English, both at the morphological, syntactic, and lexical levels. Among the three regional languages, interference from the Jakarta dialect of Malay is mostly used by private radio broadcasters in DKI.

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